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Certain Definite Integral in Association with Complete Elliptic Integral

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Abstract :

In this paper we have developed certain definite integral involving elliptic integral of first and second kind.

Keywords and Phrases : Elliptic integral, Gauss hypergeometric function, Boolean algebra.

AMS Mathematical Subject Classifications 2020 : 33C75, 33E05, 03G05.

1. Introduction :

Yurry A. Brychkov (see [2], p.155-156(4.1.6)) has established the following formulae:

$$\int_0^a \frac{1}{\sqrt{(a^2-x^2)}} \sin^{-1}(bx) dx = \frac{1}{2} [Li_2(ab) + Li_2(-ab)] \quad (1.1)$$

where $[|\arg(1-a^2b^2)| < \pi]$.

$$\int_0^a \sqrt{(a^2-x^2)} \sin^{-1}(bx) dx = \frac{a}{4b} \left\{ \frac{1-a^2b^2}{2ab} \ln \frac{1+ab}{1-ab} + ab[Li_2(ab) - Li_2(-ab)] - 1 \right\} \quad (1.2)$$

where $[|\arg(1-a^2b^2)| < \pi]$.

$$\int_0^a x \sqrt{(a^2-x^2)} \sin^{-1}(bx) dx = \frac{a^2}{9b} [2(1-2a^2b^2)D(ab) - (1-3a^2b^2)K(ab)] \quad (1.3)$$

where $[|\arg(1-a^2b^2)| < \pi]$.

And

$$\int_0^a \frac{x}{\sqrt{(a^2-x^2)}} \sin^{-1}(bx) dx = a^2b[K(ab) - D(ab)] \quad (1.4)$$

where $[|\arg(1-a^2b^2)| < \pi]$.

A generalized hypergeometric function ${}_aF_\beta(a_1, \dots, a_\alpha; b_1, \dots, b_\beta; z)$ is a function which can be defined in the form of a hypergeometric series, i.e., a series for which the ratio of successive terms can be written

$$\frac{c_{\zeta+1}}{c_\zeta} = \frac{P(\zeta)}{Q(\zeta)} = \frac{(\zeta+a_1)(\zeta+a_2)\dots(\zeta+a_\alpha)}{(\zeta+b_1)(\zeta+b_2)\dots(\zeta+b_\beta)(\zeta+1)} z. \quad (1.5)$$

Where $\zeta + 1$ in the denominator is present for historical reasons of notation (see[6], p.12(2.9)) and the resulting generalized hypergeometric function is written as under:

$${}_\alpha F_\beta \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, a_2, \dots, a_\alpha ; \\ b_1, b_2, \dots, b_\beta ; \end{matrix} z \right] = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_1)_k (a_2)_k \dots (a_\alpha)_k z^k}{(b_1)_k (b_2)_k \dots (b_\beta)_k k!} \quad (1.6)$$

where the parameters $b_1, b_2, \dots, b_\beta$ are positive integers.

The complete elliptic integral of the first kind K is defined as

$$K(\eta) = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{d\theta}{\sqrt{1 - \eta^2 \sin^2 \theta}} = \int_0^1 \frac{dt}{\sqrt{(1-t^2)(1-\eta^2 t^2)}} \quad (1.7)$$

In power series

$$K(\eta) = \frac{\pi}{2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(2n)!}{2^{2n}(n!)^2} \right]^2 \eta^{2n} = \frac{\pi}{2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} [P_{2n}(0)]^2 \eta^{2n} \quad (1.8)$$

where P_n is the Legendre polynomial.

In terms of the Gauss hypergeometric function, the complete elliptic integral of the first kind can be expressed as

$$K(\eta) = \frac{\pi}{2} {}_2F_1 \left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; \eta^2 \right) \quad (1.9)$$

The complete elliptic integral of the second kind E is defined as

$$E(\eta) = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{1 - \eta^2 \sin^2 \theta} d\theta = \int_0^1 \frac{\sqrt{1 - \eta^2 t^2}}{\sqrt{1 - t^2}} dt \quad (1.10)$$

It can be expressed as a power series

$$E(\eta) = \frac{\pi}{2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(2n)!}{2^{2n}(n!)^2} \right]^2 \frac{\eta^{2n}}{1-2n} \quad (1.11)$$

In terms of the Gauss hypergeometric function

$$E(\eta) = \frac{\pi}{2} {}_2F_1 \left(\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}; 1; \eta^2 \right) \quad (1.12)$$

The fundamental operations of Boolean algebra are as follows:

- (A). AND (conjunction), denoted $\xi \wedge \omega$, satisfies $\xi \wedge \omega = 1$ if $\xi = \omega = 1$, and $\xi \wedge \omega = 0$ otherwise.
- (B). OR (disjunction), denoted $\xi \vee \omega$, satisfies $\xi \vee \omega = 0$ if $\xi = \omega = 0$, and $\xi \vee \omega = 1$ otherwise.
- (C). NOT (negation), denoted $\neg \xi$, satisfies $\neg \xi = 0$ if $\xi = 1$ and $\neg \xi = 1$ if $\xi = 0$.

2. Main Formulae of the Integration :

In this section, we establish a set of twelve new integral formulae:

$$\int_0^a x \sqrt{a^2 - x^2} \tan^{-1}(cx) dx = \frac{\pi[a^2 c^2 (2\sqrt{a^2 c^2 + 1} - 3) + 2(\sqrt{a^2 c^2 + 1} - 1)]}{12c^3} \quad (2.1)$$

where $a > 0$.

$$\int_0^a x \sqrt{a^2 - x^2} \tanh^{-1}(cx) dx = \frac{\pi[a^2 c^2 (-2\sqrt{a^2 c^2 - 1} + 3) + 2\sqrt{a^2 c^2 - 1} - 2]}{12c^3} \quad (2.2)$$

where $c < 0 \wedge ac < -1$.

$$\int_0^a \frac{\sqrt{a^2 - x^2} \tan^{-1}(cx)}{x} dx = \frac{\pi(-\sqrt{a^2 c^2 + 1} + ac \sinh^{-1}(ac) + 1)}{2c} \quad (2.3)$$

where $c \in \mathbb{R} \wedge \operatorname{Re}(a) > 0 \wedge \operatorname{Im}(a) = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^a x \sqrt{a^2 - x^2} \sinh^{-1}(cx) dx \\ = \frac{(3a^4 c^4 + 5a^2 c^2 + 2)K(-a^2 c^2) - 2(2a^2 c^2 + 1)E(-a^2 c^2)}{9c^3} \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

where $\operatorname{Re}(c) \geq 0 \wedge \operatorname{Re}(a) > 0 \wedge \operatorname{Im}(a) = 0 \wedge (\operatorname{Im}(c) > 0 \vee \operatorname{Re}(c) > 0)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^a x^3 \sqrt{a^2 - x^2} \sinh^{-1}(cx) dx = \frac{1}{225c^5} [(a^2 c^2 + 1)(30a^4 c^4 - 7a^2 c^2 - 24)K(-a^2 c^2) \\ + (-31a^4 c^4 + 19a^2 c^2 + 24)E(-a^2 c^2)] \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

where $\text{Re}(c) \geq 0 \wedge \text{Re}(a) > 0 \wedge \text{Im}(a) = 0 \wedge (\text{Im}(c) > 0 \vee \text{Re}(c) > 0)$.

$$\int_0^a x^5 \sqrt{a^2 - x^2} \sinh^{-1}(cx) dx = \frac{1}{11025c^7} [(a^2c^2 + 1)(840a^6c^6 - 241a^4c^4 + 48a^2c^2 + 720)K(-a^2c^2) - 2(389a^6c^6 - 176a^4c^4 + 204a^2c^2 + 360)E(-a^2c^2)] \quad (2.6)$$

where $a > 0 \wedge c > 0$.

$$\int_0^a \frac{\sqrt{a^2 - x^2} \sinh^{-1}(cx)}{x} dx = \frac{1}{4} \pi a^2 c {}_3F_2 \left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}, 2; -a^2c^2 \right) \quad (2.7)$$

where $\text{Re}(c) \geq 0 \wedge \text{Re}(a) > 0 \wedge \text{Im}(a) = 0 \wedge (\text{Im}(c) > 0 \vee \text{Re}(c) > 0)$.

$$\int_0^a \frac{x \sinh^{-1}(cx)}{\sqrt{a^2 - x^2}} dx = \frac{(a^2c^2 + 1)K(-a^2c^2) - E(-a^2c^2)}{c} \quad (2.8)$$

where $\text{Re}(c) \geq 0 \wedge \text{Re}(a) > 0 \wedge \text{Im}(a) = 0 \wedge (\text{Im}(c) > 0 \vee \text{Re}(c) > 0)$.

$$\int_0^a \frac{x^3 \sinh^{-1}(cx)}{\sqrt{a^2 - x^2}} dx = \frac{(-5a^2c^2 + 2)E(-a^2c^2) + (3a^4c^4 + 2a^2c^2 - 1)K(-a^2c^2)}{9c^3} \quad (2.9)$$

where $\text{Re}(c) \geq 0 \wedge \text{Re}(a) > 0 \wedge \text{Im}(a) = 0 \wedge (\text{Im}(c) > 0 \vee \text{Re}(c) > 0)$.

$$\int_0^a \frac{x^5 \sinh^{-1}(cx)}{\sqrt{a^2 - x^2}} dx = \frac{1}{225c^5} [(-94a^4c^4 + 31a^2c^2 - 24)E(-a^2c^2) + (120a^6c^6 + 77a^4c^4 - 19a^2c^2 + 24)K(-a^2c^2)] \quad (2.10)$$

where $\text{Re}(c) \geq 0 \wedge \text{Re}(a) > 0 \wedge \text{Im}(a) = 0 \wedge (\text{Im}(c) > 0 \vee \text{Re}(c) > 0)$.

$$\int_0^a \frac{x^7 \sinh^{-1}(cx)}{\sqrt{a^2 - x^2}} dx = \frac{1}{3675c^7} [(-1276a^6c^6 + 389a^4c^4 - 256a^2c^2 + 240)E(-a^2c^2) + 2(840a^8c^8 + 529a^6c^6 - 123a^4c^4 + 68a^2c^2 - 120)K(-a^2c^2)] \quad (2.11)$$

where $\text{Re}(c) \geq 0 \wedge \text{Re}(a) > 0 \wedge \text{Im}(a) = 0 \wedge (\text{Im}(c) > 0 \vee \text{Re}(c) > 0)$.

$$\int_0^a \frac{x^9 \sinh^{-1}(cx)}{\sqrt{a^2-x^2}} dx = \frac{1}{99225c^9} [(a^2c^2+1)(40320a^8c^8 - 15208a^6c^6 + 9549a^4c^4 - 6600a^2c^2 + 4480) K(-a^2c^2) + (-30064a^8c^8 + 8776a^6c^6 - 5409a^4c^4 + 4360a^2c^2 - 4480) E(-a^2c^2)] \quad (2.12)$$

where $\text{Re}(c) \geq 0 \wedge \text{Re}(a) > 0 \wedge \text{Im}(a) = 0 \wedge (\text{Im}(c) > 0 \vee \text{Re}(c) > 0)$.

$$\int_0^a \frac{x^{11} \sinh^{-1}(cx)}{\sqrt{a^2-x^2}} dx = \frac{1}{2401245c^{11}} [2(a^2c^2+1)(a^2c^2(443520a^8c^8 - 169304a^6c^6 + 108693a^4c^4 - 78081a^2c^2 + 57344) - 40320) K(-a^2c^2) + (a^2c^2(-653344a^8c^8 + 185512a^6c^6 - 110241a^4c^4 + 83698a^2c^2 - 743368) + 80640)E(-a^2c^2)] \quad (2.13)$$

where $\text{Re}(c) \geq 0 \wedge \text{Re}(a) > 0 \wedge \text{Im}(a) = 0 \wedge (\text{Im}(c) > 0 \vee \text{Re}(c) > 0)$.

3. Derivation of Main Formulae :

Proof of (2.1) :

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^a x \sqrt{a^2-x^2} \tan^{-1}(cx) dx \\ &= \left[-\frac{1}{6c^3} \left(2c^3(a^2-x^2)^{3/2} \tan^{-1}(cx) + c^2x \sqrt{a^2-x^2} + (3a^2c^2+2) \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{a^2-x^2}}\right) \right) \right. \\ & \quad + \iota(a^2c^2+1)^{3/2} \log \left(\frac{12c^4(-\iota\sqrt{a^2c^2+1}\sqrt{a^2-x^2} - \iota a^2c + x)}{(a^2c^2+1)^{5/2}(cx+\iota)} \right) \\ & \quad \left. - \iota(a^2c^2+1)^{3/2} \log \left(\frac{12c^4(\iota\sqrt{a^2c^2+1}\sqrt{a^2-x^2} + \iota a^2c + x)}{(a^2c^2+1)^{5/2}(cx-\iota)} \right) \right]_0^a \end{aligned}$$

applying the properties of definit integral we have,

$$= \frac{\pi[a^2c^2(2\sqrt{a^2c^2+1}-3) + 2(\sqrt{a^2c^2+1}-1)]}{12c^3}, \quad \text{where } a > 0.$$

We thus have completed our proof of (2.1).

Proofs of (2.2) - (2.13) : The proofs of (2.2) - (2.13) are on the similar pattern to the proof of (2.1). Hence, we left the proof for the readers.

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Conflicts of Interest : All the four authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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